

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF ENGINEER BUILDERS ON THE BASE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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ANNOTATION

This article explores the training of highly qualified technical personnel, their formation as a comprehensively developed person and the competency characteristics in them. Using methods of systematic analysis, the state of competency properties is evaluated through the observation method, and relevant conclusions are formed through abstract-logical thinking.

Keywords: *competence, professional competence, competence, efficiency, professional activity, professional action, psihological-pedagogical, knowledge, skills*

INTRODUCTION. The system of training highly qualified technical personnel is currently undergoing major changes. The formation of a specialist is inextricably linked with the level of professional training. It can be seen that the modern education system is developing taking into account the formation of the market economy, the level of development of society's information and production technologies. Currently, competence is often defined as the ability to combine knowledge and skills, methods of their use, in the context of changing environmental requirements.[1] Competence is an integral quality of a person formed during the implementation of professional actions, including qualities and characteristics of a specialist, his motives, knowledge, skills, abilities, responsibilities. An important component of human professional skills is professional competence. The study of psychological-pedagogical literature and

other informational literature shows that the term "professional competence" is defined by several approaches. Foreign researchers often consider this concept as "deep knowledge", "state of adequate performance of actions", "ability to perform activities in practice", "effectiveness of actions". In local psychological and pedagogical literature, the following definition of the term "professional competence" is considered: "the quality, property or condition of a specialist that ensures his physical, mental and spiritual compliance with the needs and conditions of any profession. Professional competence is one of the main cognitive components of the subsystem of professionalism of activity, a field of professional behavior, a constantly developing system of knowledge that allows the implementation of professional activity, a number of issues or problems that must be solved with high productivity [2].

Competence is considered as a combination of mental qualities, i.e. As a person's ability and ability to perform certain labor functions, the mental state that allows independent and responsible action, that is, the essence of professional competence is expressed at the level of correlation between the objective standard of professional activity.[12] The professional competence of an engineer-builder means professional and personal significant qualities of a specialist, including practical experience in designing and constructing buildings and structures, organizing the work of structural units, implementing technological processes and organizational work. We list the pedagogical conditions that ensure the effective development of professional qualifications of construction specialists:

- implementation of high-quality and timely formation of qualifications and, if necessary, correction of this process;
- constantly updating and enriching the information-educational environment of educational institutions;
- use of educational and methodological complexes;
- creating a motivational environment aimed at forming the student's self-awareness and outlook; focus on self-learning, self-development, and self-improvement both during schooling and throughout life. A construction technician must participate in the implementation of his professional functions, in the design of

buildings and structures; implementation of technological processes in the construction, use and reconstruction of construction sites; organizing the work of structural units in the execution of construction and assembly works, operation, repair and reconstruction of buildings and structures; organization of types of work in operation and reconstruction of construction objects. Thus, the main professional competencies that form the basis of the skills of an engineer-builder can be summarized as follows:

- instruments containing general knowledge of the profession, including basic skills;
- interpersonal relationship, ability to work in a group, ability to self-criticize, attraction to ethnic values, tolerance;
- systematic, systematic application of acquired knowledge in practice, creation of new ideas, adaptation to new situations;
- the ability to master a special, scientific field at a certain quality level.

Practice-oriented educational technology helps to increase the efficiency and quality of education. The goal of practice-oriented education is to develop cognitive needs, search for new knowledge, and increase the effectiveness of the educational process. The basis of practice-oriented education is the organization of an educational process based on the acquisition of new knowledge and the formation of practical experience and use in solving tasks and problems of professional importance.

Research methodology. The methodological basis of the research is devoted to the issues of determining the characteristics of competence. In the process of analysis, comparison and systematic analysis methods were used. The state of competence characteristics was assessed through the observation method and relevant conclusions were formed through abstract-logical thinking.

Conclusions and suggestions. The qualities necessary for a modern civil engineer lead to the need to form fundamental knowledge and determine the ways to acquire the engineering profession. The given professional quality of subjects of engineering activity.

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